

IPBES TCA Chapter 3. Review of knowledge on theories and frameworks of transformative change / IPBES transformative change assessment (3.1)

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Description

The review corresponds to the IPBES transformative change assessment. The IPBES Scoping document for the transformative change assessment describes that chapter 3 should address how transformative change occurs, focusing on those changes that can be intentionally promoted, accelerated, and scaled to realize a sustainable world where biodiversity can thrive. The chapter provides evidence on theories and frameworks for understanding deliberate, or emergent transformative change. In this context, a review of knowledge focused on theories and frameworks of transformative change was conducted and is further described below.

Process overview

Protocol

Process 1: Selection of theories and frameworks for Transformative Change

Chapter 3 experts were asked for input through Google Forms (**R1**) on relevant theories and frameworks that provide knowledge on how transformative change occurs, as well as other theories and frameworks that provide insights on how transformative change occurs without explicitly using the terms.

Details search 1:

Chapter 3 experts were invited to share relevant references associated with each theory and framework and to answer twelve sets of questions (**R1**) (including but not limited to how transformative change occurs according to each theory and framework; their main assumptions; how they address norms, values; direct and indirect drivers of change, power and agency) aiming to understand the implication of each theory and framework for understanding the conditions and process for generating and navigating transformative change. A detailed Excel spreadsheet was set up as an initial and internal database (synthesised in Annex 3.2 of Chapter 3).

This method allowed the identification of references to build clusters of theories and frameworks of transformative change, and its results are included in sections 3.2 and 3.3.

Process 2: Experts survey for identifying transformative change theories and frameworks:

To complement the first expert review phase, a second round of literature identification was conducted through an online expert survey in Google Forms provided to all experts of the transformative change assessment.

- **Questions asked:**
 - Most relevant theories and frameworks that describes how intentional transformative change occurs,
 - Name up to two main references and
 - Name up to two potential contributing authors for each theory and framework.
- **Extracted sample:** The outcome of this survey resulted in 105 responses.
- **Treatment applied:** An internal review was carried out to assess the relevance of the suggested theory and framework for transformative change to sustainability, eliminate duplicates and redundancies. This process resulted in a total of 62 theories and frameworks (including the 16 previously described in Table 1). This final set of identified theories and frameworks has been assessed and various experts have been contacted to collaborate as contributing authors in the assessment. Contributing authors were asked to contribute their expertise on the identified theories and frameworks (including giving a brief description of the theory and framework, a summary of how transformative change occurs, and references). In the course of time, 39 theories and frameworks are included in Annex 3.2 as examples of theories and frameworks describing how transformative change occurs from diverse disciplines and perspectives identified with the primary and secondary clusters they represent. Following revisions and edits of the

chapter, based on their expert knowledge, experts from Chapter 3 have included a third emerging list of relevant references on theories and frameworks **(B)**.

This method allowed the contrast of clusters of theories and frameworks of transformative change, and its results are included in section 3.2, but mostly 3.3.

The following 62 theories and frameworks for which detailed descriptions were obtained were selected to be presented in a chapter annex:

1. Systems approaches

- Human agency
- Agroecological transformations
- Phases of deliberate social-ecological transformations
- Panarchy theory
- Catalysing transformation
- Seeds of the good anthropocene
- Collective action in social-ecological systems
- Integrative framework for transformative social change
- Sustainability transitions
- Social movements theories
- Transition governance
- Leverage points for sustainability transformation
- Transformation flower approach
- Metatheories of human action
- Redesigning theories of change
- Value-centred leverage points to catalyse transformative change
- Regenerative approaches

2. Structural approaches

- Karl Polanyi's "The Great Transformation"
- Marxist theory
- Rational choice theory
- Institutional analysis
- Ecological civilization framework
- Governmentality
- Degrowth and post-growth studies
- Strengthening accountability frameworks
- Biodiversity policy integration
- Transition management
- Behavioural economics
- International political economy
- Transformative governance
- Environmental State and the green State
- Structuration theory
- Social practice theory
- Actor network theory

3. Inner transformation

- Inner transformation
- Pathways to nature connectedness
- Relationality
- Regenerative dialogues for sustainable futures
- SHIFT
- Transformative learning for social-ecological sustainability
- Relational values and relationality

4. Empowerment

- Political ecology
- Transformative spaces
- Three spheres of transformation
- Praxis
- Environmental history: environmentalism of the poors and environmental coloniality
- Fractal agency
- Everyday resistance
- Feminist political ecology
- Decolonial feminisms and ecofeminism

5. Knowledge co-creation

- Three horizons
- Ethnoecology
- Sustainability science
- Participatory research
- Transformative education
- Local Biodiversity Outlook (LBO) transitions
- Transdisciplinary research
- Transformative innovation policy

6. Science and technology

- Epistemic communities
- Inclusive innovation
- Science and technology, systems
- Technological and scientific constructivism

Process 3: Snowball search on reference papers provided by contributing authors for each theory and framework

A snowball search has been conducted to include the papers cited by the reference papers (provided by contributing authors in the previous step) that explain how transformative change occurs according to each theory and framework. Figure 1 below shows the distribution of publications for each approach.

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** snowball search
- **Search engine:** OpenAlex
- **Sample extracted:**
 - Cluster 1: 5716 references
 - Cluster 2: 23313 references
 - Cluster 3: 50701 references
 - Cluster 4: 38695 references
 - Cluster 5: 3914 references
 - Cluster 6: 59182 references
- **Treatment applied:** Although there is some overlap between the approaches, it illustrates how different the literature linked to each approach is and consolidates the distribution into 6 distinct approaches:
 - Science and technology approach: 4 theories and frameworks
 - Knowledge co-creation approach: 11 theories and frameworks
 - Inner transformation approach: 9 theories and frameworks
 - Systems approach: 18 theories and frameworks
 - Empowerment approach: 10 theories and frameworks
 - Structural approach: 18 theories and frameworks

Only the references cited for the theories and frameworks identified as mainly associated to each of the six approaches were included in the analysis. For example, 18 theories and frameworks are mainly relevant for systems approaches and about 90 references were cited. The snowball search was conducted on these 90 references:

- Science and technology approach: 4 theories and frameworks*5 = 20 references
- Knowledge co-creation approach: 11 theories and frameworks*5 = 55 references
- Inner transformation approach: 9 theories and frameworks*5 = 45 references
- Systems approach: 18 theories and frameworks*5 = 90 references
- Empowerment approach: 10 theories and frameworks*5 = 50 references
- Structural approach: 18 theories and frameworks*5 = 90 references

Figure 1. Snowball search for theories and frameworks under each of the six approaches

See GitHub repository for further detailed information on the snowball search conducted and its results:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11381693>

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	1_IPBES_TCA_DMR 3.1_11_2024_(A)	PDF	199 KB	List of references selected on theories and frameworks of transformative change.
B	2_IPBES_TCA_DMR 3.1_11_2024_(B)	PDF	208 KB	Third emerging list of relevant references on theories and frameworks
R1	3_IPBES_TCA_DMR 3.1_11_2024_(R1)	PDF	123 KB	List of questions from Google form survey to chapter 3 authors